

SYNTHESIS OF MCM-41 FROM COAL FLY ASH

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Abstract

Efficient recycling of and resource recovery from coal fly ash (CFA) has been a major topic of current international research interest, aimed at achieving sustainable development of human society from the viewpoints of energy, economy, and environmental strategy. This study reported a novel, green and fast method to produce pure and long-range ordered nano-porous MCM-41 material from CFA. Performance evaluation of the produced MCM-41 material in wastewater treatment was investigated. Compared to the commercial zeolite A (Valfor 100), adsorbents produced from CFA were effective in removing multi heavy metal ions in water and could be an alternative material for treatment of wastewater.

1 Introduction

MCM-41 has a hexagonal structure with uni-dimensional pore structure with pore size ranging from 2-50 nm. Several environmental and energy technologies can emerge with substantial benefits from MCM-41 material, including basic science, air purification and waste remediation [1-2]. However, the use of MCM-41 in these areas, especially environmental remediation, are restricted due to prohibitive production cost [3].

Coal fly ash (CFA) is the waste product of combustion of coal in a coal-fired power station. The global annual production of CFA is about 800 million tons and this amount is predicted to increase in the future [4]. However, the global recycling rate of CFA is only 15% posing important challenges in waste management. At present, efficient disposal of CFA is a worldwide issue because of its massive production and its harmful effects on the environment [5]. Resource recovery from CFA can be one of the approaches to speed up reuse of CFA, since the major chemical compositions contained in CFA are SiO₂ and Al₂O₃ (60-70 wt% and 16-20 wt%, respectively) [6]. Although CFA has been reused in highway construction, land reclamation

and restoration of eroded soil, the demand for such applications is still limited [7]. Converting CFA into MCM-41 material is one of the approaches to recycle CFA. However, most of the studies applied a long conversion time (1-3 days) to produce MCM-41 materials from CFA and the materials produced still contained a significant amount of residual CFA [3, 8-10]. Thus, the potential applicability of the MCM-41 materials is greatly reduced.

The presence of heavy metal ions in streams and lakes has been responsible for several types of health problems in animals, plants and human beings [11]. There has been little investigation on using CFA converted MCM-41 (without residues of CFA) in wastewater treatment. Removing heavy metal ions in contaminated water using low-cost materials may lead to substantial economic and environmental benefits. Knowledge on application of CFA converted MCM-41 material in waste water treatment could be useful in designing alternative cheaper wastewater.

This paper reported a green approach to produce MCM-41 from CFA, which can be an important contribution to the large scale production of MCM-41 material. This approach took 24 h at 25 °C to produce 9 g of MCM-41 materials from 30 g of the CFA, which is the shortest time and lowest reaction temperature required to produce pure and ordered MCM-41 materials (having the largest internal surface area) compared to the values reported in the literature. Performance evaluation of the produced MCM-41 material in wastewater treatment was investigated.

2 Experiments

2.1 Coal Fly Ash

The CFA used in this project was obtained from a power plant in the southern part of China and was used in each experiment after pretreatment at 120 °C for 30 min in an oven. The size of the CFA, determined by a particle size analyzer (Coulter LS230), covers a range from 0.04 to 600 μm and

with an average diameter of 20.7 μm . The chemical composition of the CFA was analyzed by XRF (JEOL JSX-3201Z) and is listed in Table 1. The amounts of crystallized and amorphous SiO_2 in the CFA are 3.9 and 46.2 wt% respectively, which was assayed by a quantitative X-ray diffraction (XRD) method [12]. The BET surface area of the CFA is 1.4 m^2/g .

2.2 Production of MCM-41 from Coal Fly Ash

A green, cost-effective and fast method for production of MCM-41 was developed. Inexpensive CFA as an inorganic silica source instead of expensive ones was used in the production process. Ethyl acetate as a mild acid hydrolyser was used in the production of MCM-41 material under environmentally friendly conditions where no toxic waste was generated. This approach can be an important improvement to the industrial scale production of MCM-41 materials. The production process was carried out as follows. The amorphous SiO_2 component in the CFA was used as Si source for the production of MCM-41. **Extraction of Si source:** Mixture of 30 g of CFA and 300 ml of 2M NaOH solution in a 1 l sealed PP bottle was kept in an oil bath at 100 $^\circ\text{C}$ for 4.5 h under stirred condition (300 rpm). Then the solution was separated from the mixture by a filtration process. The amounts of Si, Al and Na in the extracted solution (denoted as Si solution) were 5470 mg/l, 518 mg/l and 14900 mg/l, respectively (analyzed by ICP-AES, Perkin-Elmer 3000 XL). The residual was labeled as the treated CFA residue (TCFAR). **Preparation of MCM-41 source solution:** MCM-41 source solution was prepared following the procedure described in the literature [13] with modification. At 85 $^\circ\text{C}$ and under stirring at 300 rpm, 82 ml of the Si solution was mixed with 1 g of CTAB to obtain an aqueous solution. Then, under stirring at 600 rpm, 3.1 ml of ethyl acetate was rapidly added into the solution. After stirring the mixture for 10 min, the obtained solution was cooled down to room temperature (25 $^\circ\text{C}$) by natural convection. The resultant solution was denoted as M solution in this study. **Production of MCM-41:** 10 ml of M solution was adjusted to pH of 6.9 by the addition of a few drops of 5.25 N H_2SO_4 solution under slow stirring (50 rpm). Precipitation was observed during pH adjustment. The pH adjusted solution was kept at room temperature (25 $^\circ\text{C}$) for 24 h. The material obtained was washed with deionised water and dried at 100 $^\circ\text{C}$ for 2 h. The dried material was calcined

under air at 550 $^\circ\text{C}$ for 4 h at a heating rate of 1 $^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$. The material was denoted as CFAMCM.

2.3 Characterization of Samples

The pH values of the aqueous solutions were measured with a Mettler-Toledo meter (MP 120). The bulk elemental composition of the samples were determined by a JEOL X-ray reflective fluorescence spectrometer (XRF, JSX 3201Z). Powder X-ray diffraction (XRD) patterns of the samples were obtained using a powder diffractometer (Philips PW 1830) equipped with a $\text{CuK}\alpha$ radiation. The accelerating voltage and current used were 40 kV and 20 mA, respectively. The scanning range of 2θ was set between 2° and 50° , with a step size of 0.02° and $0.01^\circ/\text{s}$. Nitrogen adsorption/desorption was carried out at 77 K using the Coulter SA3100 nitrogen physic-adsorption apparatus. The volume of adsorbed nitrogen was normalized to standard temperature and pressure (STP). Prior to the experiments, the samples were dehydrated at 150 $^\circ\text{C}$ for 3 h. The BET surface area was determined from the linear part of the BET plot ($p/p_0 = 0.05\text{-}0.2$). Surface morphology of the samples was analyzed by scanning electronic microscopy (SEM, JEOL 6300) coupled with energy dispersive X-ray analysis (EDAX). All metal concentrations were analyzed using Inductively Coupled Plasma Atomic Emission Spectrometry (ICP-AES, Perkin-Elmer 3000 XL).

2.4 Waste Water Treatment

The experiments of sorption capacity were performed in a batch reactor (250 ml) at 25 ± 0.5 $^\circ\text{C}$ with continuous stirring at 600 rpm. The adsorbents (0.5 g) were left in contact with 100 ml of multi-metal-ions solution in the range of each metal ions of 50 to 300 mg/l with the initial pH value of 3 for 240 min. The filtrates were filtered with 0.45 μm filter and acidified with 2% HNO_3 to decrease the pH to below 3 before the ICP-AES measurement. In order to obtain the sorption capacity, the amount of ions adsorbed per unit mass of adsorbent (q_e in milligram of metal ions per gram of adsorbent) was evaluated using the following expression:

$$q_e = \frac{C_o - C_e}{m} V \quad (1)$$

where C_o is the initial metal ion concentration (mg/l), C_e is the equilibrium metal ion concentration (mg/l), V is the volume of the aqueous phase (l), and m is the amount of the adsorbent used (g).

3 Results and Discussions

3.1 Characterization of the Adsorbents

Table 1 shows the chemical composition of the CFA, TCFAR, the commercial zeolite A (Valfor 100) and the CFAMCM. The main components of the CFA and the TCFAR were oxides of Si and Al, and various metallic oxides. Apparently, the presence of impurity elements Mg and Fe in the TCFAR may be due to the incorporation of these elements during the crystallization. These elements were thought to be present as soluble oxides in CFA and were expected to form oxy-anions upon dissolution under alkaline conditions during the extraction of Si source from CFA. The incorporation of aluminum was generally accompanied by Na⁺ ions to balance the charge of the CFAMCM sample. As shown in Table 1, the BET surface area of TCFAR increased 13-fold from the CFA. This increase in BET surface area is due to crystallization of zeolite NaP1 crystals on the outer surface of the CFA. The BET surface area of the Valfor 100 is 71.4 m²/g. The BET surface area of the CFAMCM is 953 m²/g, which is higher than the reported value in literature [9].

Fig.1 shows the morphology of the various adsorbents. The CFA consists of smooth spheres of diameter of 0.04 - 600 μm and has a mean diameter of 20.7 μm. These particles were formed from the cooling of molten products after the combustion of clay compounds in the original coal. By contrast, the morphology of the TCFAR was rough (1 - 10 μm, with a mean diameter of 3 μm), appearing as aggregates of small plates. This was because zeolite crystals (Na-P1) were precipitated out on the surface of the CFA particles. The morphology of the Valfor 100 was chamfered-edged cube. The chamfered-edged cube morphology was due to the initial SiO₂/Al₂O₃ concentration used in the production process. The particle size of the Valfor 100 was 1-3 μm with a mean diameter of 2 μm. The particle size of the CFAMCM was around 0.15 μm.

Fig. 2 shows the XRD patterns of the adsorbents. The crystalline species in the CFA sample are quartz, mullite, calcite, portlandite, anhydrite, hematite and gehlenite as identified by the sharp peaks, while the presence of the amorphous phases of SiO₂ are identified by the presence of a broad diffraction peak (near 2θ = 24°). Quartz and mullite were produced during the thermal decomposition of clay minerals such as kaolinite during combustion. The TCFAR was identified as a mixture of zeolite Na-P1 (JCPDS card 39-0219) and calcite (CaCO₃, JCPDS card 05-0586). For the CFAMCM, the {1 0 0} reflection was observed, which represents the characteristics of the hexagonal lattice symmetry of the MCM-41

structure. However, the peaks, corresponding to, {1 1 0}, {2 0 0} and {2 1 0} reflection, of the sample were broadened and weakened, and the deterioration of the long range ordering structure of the sample was observed. These might be due to the incorporation of metal elements into the sample causing structural irregularity.

3.2 Removal Efficiency of Multi-metal-ions by the CFA, TCFAR, Valfor 100 and CFAMCM

The kinetics study showed that around 90% of the metal ions were removed in the first 60 min. No significant adsorption was detected after 240 min of stirring under all the experimental conditions. Table 2 lists the equilibrium sorption capacity of each metal ion by different adsorbents. The original CFA had the lowest equilibrium sorption capacity of the metal ions at the tested concentrations. Besides, it was interesting that the TCFAR had a relatively high equilibrium sorption capacity of the metal ions (except Co²⁺ ions) than the commercial zeolite A (Valfor 100). The high equilibrium sorption capacity of the metal ions by the TCFAR was caused by the high alkalinity of the sample (pH ~ 11) and the existence of zeolite NaP1 on the outer surface of the sample. The main mechanisms of removal of metal ions by the TCFAR were due to adsorption and precipitation formation; while by the zeolite A (Valfor 100) was due to ion-exchange and adsorption.

Table 2 also shows that the CFAMCM (without any functional organic groups grafted onto the surface of the sample) are poor adsorbent for the removal of multi heavy metal ions. However, studies have shown that the sorption capacity of metal ions by MCM-41 samples can be significantly improved through post-modification of the MCM-41 samples to improve its affinity to metal ions [14]. The CFAMCM possessed a large pore size (0.32 nm), pore volume (0.9 cm³/g), BET surface area (953 m²/g) and good hydrothermal stability. These properties enabled them to accommodate a larger concentration of functional groups on their surface. It has been shown that the sorption capacity of metal ions increases with increasing concentration of the grafted functional group. It is expected that the CFAMCM can be used as an adsorbent in the treatment of waste water after grafting functional organic groups (such as thiol or amine) onto its surface.

4 Conclusions

Compared to the commercial zeolite A (Valfor 100), adsorbents produced from CFA were effective in removing multi heavy metal ions in water and could be alternative materials for treatment of wastewater. This study provides the guidance for production of MCM-41 from CFA by a cost-effective approach which opens potential applications of these materials in environmental industry.

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Fig. 1. SEM pictures of the adsorbents.

Fig. 2. XRD patterns of the adsorbents. M, Q, C, P, A, H and G represent mullite, quartz, calcite, portlandite, anhydrite, hematite and gehlenite, respectively.

Table 1
Chemical composition and BET surface area of the samples

Composition (wt%)	CFA	TCFAR	Valfor 100	CFAMCM
SiO ₂	50.09	43.34	44.68	95.17
Al ₂ O ₃	24.91	35.71	34.91	1.16
Na ₂ O	0.14	19.75	20.12	1.49
CaO	11.77	-	-	-
MgO	0.40	0.25	0.18	-
Fe ₂ O ₃	7.60	0.80	-	-
BET surface area (m ² /g)	1.4	22.2	71.4	953

- = not available

Table 2
Equilibrium sorption capacity of multi-metal-ions by the adsorbents

Initial conc. (mg/l)	Adsorbent	Equilibrium sorption capacity (mg/g)				
		Co ²⁺	Cr ³⁺	Cu ²⁺	Ni ²⁺	Zn ²⁺
300	CFA	1.2	10.0	15.2	2.0	4.0
	TCFAR	8.8	48.7	55.0	9.2	30.3
	Valfor 100	11.2	44.5	51.1	7.6	25.8
	CFAMCM	9.65	12.28	13.16	7.89	14.91